

Are Moroccan Universities Ready for Knowledge Management

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Abstract: throughout the literature, several factors affect positively KM initiatives in universities are discussed. Some of these are the same as those found for private organizations and others are specific to public organizations. Most authors cite the organizational culture and structure.

The main objective of this study was to verify the presence of success factors in KM implementation at the Moroccan universities via Abdelmalek Essaadi University subject of this work.

through a deductive reasoning approach and a quantitative working method, Using the questionnaire as a tool to collect data from a proportional random and representative sample of 88 teacher-researchers from the different institutions of the university under study.

The study found a positive relationship between the requirements for Knowledge management (organizational culture, organizational structure,) and KM application in Moroccan universities with a Pearson correlation rate $R = 0.712$ For organizational culture and 0.576 for organizational structure.

also, the results obtained show insufficiency presence of initiatives for a knowledge management implementation, with an average of 2.02 for organizational structure, and 1.89 concerning organizational culture according to the university's teachers.

Keywords: organizational culture, organizational structure, knowledge management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Peter F. Drucker was one of the first visionary authors to anticipate the emergence of the new economy propelled by knowledge. He remarked that “Knowledge, during the last few decades, has become the central capital, the cost center, and the crucial resource of the economy. He coined for this new economy the terms “knowledge economy”, and “knowledge work”.

Within the framework of the knowledge economy and the new challenges raised by knowledge in organizations, it is easy to understand the emergence of knowledge management as a new managerial field of activity dealing with knowledge resources, knowledge workers, and knowledge processes. Knowledge management does not replace the classical management dealing with tangible resources, but it enriches a firm's management with its capacity of dealing with intangible resources and their specific processes of creation, acquisition, sharing, transferring, transformation, and use in the production of goods and services. In addition, knowledge management is not an extrapolation of information management focused on the efficient use of information technology and data and information as intangible resources. (Bratianu et al, 2021).

in this changed competitive technology and the market scenario, Modern institutions, including institutions of higher education, face Large and unprecedented challenges due to the changes resulting from the information and technological revolution, in addition to the fierce competition between different institutions and the challenges that have emerged in the various sectors, especially the educational ones, so it was necessary to face this competition and challenges in order to keep pace The wheel of change and facing the competition imposed by the advanced reality on the basis of science and knowledge .

On the other hand, and throughout the literature, several factors positively affecting KM initiatives in public organizations and specifically in universities are discussed. For Ranjan and Bhavnagar (2008), these are factors or parameters necessary for the continued success of an organization and these factors represent the areas of management that require special and continuous attention to achieve high performance. Some are the same as those identified for private organizations and others are specific to public organizations. Most authors (Butler & Murphy, 2007; Cong, 2008; Ansari et al. 2012) cite several factors; but in this article, we will focus on the organizational culture and structure.

several studies have shown the importance of organizational culture to support the implementation of the KM process, because under a knowledge-friendly culture, the implementation of KM practice is more effective and efficient (Adeinat and Abdulfatch 2019, Danish et al. 2012, Gupta and Govindarajan (2000) Davenport and Prusak (1998).

An open culture characterized by employee participation and employee initiatives is conducive to creating and sharing knowledge. A flexible culture, however, promotes pro-activeness to changes. A culture of individualism where one wants to dominate discourages knowledge transfer, while in an organization that fosters cooperation, knowledge sharing and knowledge transfer are high (Ahmadi et al 2016). A learning culture that emphasizes continuous learning is thus essential and brings success to knowledge management (Goran & Sağsanb, 2021).

Also an organizational structure must be flexible to promote the distribution of knowledge within the organization. In contrast, a centralized and overly formalized structure will prevent communication between units and the profusion of the distribution of ideas. The communication channels will not favor a fluid diffusion and efficient sharing of knowledge. structure was particularly highlighted as a factor affecting the successful implementation of KM. Thus, horizontal organizations are more convenient for the information and knowledge era due to the flexibility that this type of organization offers (Ansari et al. 2012).

The purpose of the present research is to analyze the existence of success factors K.M implementation and more specifically the culture and structure at the Moroccan universities through the Abdelmalek Essaadi University subject of this work.

The research question we try to answer is the following: are the Moroccan universities ready for the application of K.M. the research question RQ will be decomposed into three subsidiary research questions as follows:

RQ1: there is a relationship between culture and structure of Moroccan universities and their level of K.M application ?

RQ2: the current organizational culture of Moroccan universities allows K.M implementation?

RQ3: the current organizational structure of Moroccan universities allows K.M application?

Thus, our reflection will focus on the treatment and analysis of the following three elements: (1) Literature review and development of hypotheses (2) Research methodology and (3) discussion of the Results of the study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIZES DEVELOPMENT

1. KM at university

Knowledge management developed mostly in the knowledge-intensive organizations because of the dominance of intangible resources and knowledge capabilities. Universities are such knowledge-intensive organizations, and that is a crucial argument as to why knowledge management impacts the whole academic management and leadership as well as the students' education. Although universities are based on teaching and learning processes, they are not, by definition, learning organizations. They must develop powerful knowledge management systems and design knowledge strategies for becoming learning organizations characterized by generative learning processes (Shattuck 2006, Bratianu & Pinzaru, 2015).

Also, K.M plays an important role in the development of institutions, especially universities, because of its intellectual and knowledge assets. Therefore, it has become more capable of keeping pace with development and achieving excellence in the knowledge society (Arqawi et al, 2018).

Universities are knowledge-intensive organizations because all the basic processes employ data, information, and knowledge. Teaching is essentially a transfer of knowledge from professors to students, but it involves many activities and tasks of data, information, and knowledge collection, selection, structuring, and integration into ideas and theories, which correspond to a certain conceptual framework. Teaching can be performed directly in classrooms or online by using specialized platforms and indirectly through a series of printed materials or stored documents in databases. Teaching also involves knowledge sharing that reflects professors' experience (Bratianu et al, 2021).

1.1 KM PROCESS IN UNIVERSITIES

Knowledge assets are managed in several ways, namely: through capitalization, sharing, and knowledge creation.

There is no unified agreement among authors and researchers regarding the number of K.M processes, as different researchers define them in different ways (Costa & Monterio, 2016) and with several models as they are defined as three stages: knowledge generation, knowledge codification, and knowledge transfer. Or four consisting of Acquiring, storing, sharing, and applying knowledge or it is a five-step process consisting of (knowledge acquisition, knowledge formation, knowledge transfer, knowledge storage, and application) (Abidi et al 2018, p 5).

Becerra et al, (2004) integrated the empirical research findings of Nonaka (1994) (socialization, externalization, internalization, combination), and distinguished four knowledge management processes: knowledge discovery, knowledge capture, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application.

On our part in this work, we will opt for the most used model and the most adapted to the universities in four stages consisting of acquiring, storing, sharing, and using knowledge, (Alavi & leidner, 2001, Doueih, 2009).

2. ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

the concept of organizational culture is not new. For a long time, organizational leaders have sought to create an "in-house spirit", characterizing the specificity of their know-how facing competitors. In this first observation, organizational culture allows the organization to stand out from those around it.

Organizational culture is the process of the values, beliefs, habits and behaviour that directs and influences an individual's behaviours in the organization (Khan et al. 2020). According to Eskiler et al. (2016), OC is the method of beliefs and values that shape the employees' behaviours in an organization (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy 2021).

Schein (2010) defined OC as "a basic unstated assumption of the world about how people decide their perceptions, feelings, and thoughts about their behaviours." Further, (Quinn 1988) proposed a competing values framework (CVF) model, which describes four types of culture in the organization, such as clan culture, adhocracy culture, hierarchy culture and market culture. (Cameron and Quinn 1999) defined OC as how things are around here (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy 2021).

Otherwise, and according to Thévenet (2006) organizational culture is a set of shared values, rites, myths, symbols and the history of the organization. Therefore, for Schein (2004), organizational culture is a pattern of basic assumptions shared by a group as a result of their experience addressing the issue of adaptation to external factors as well as internal integration issues. It also generates a mechanism to adapt and change (Chandradewini, 2017).

2.1 KM AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

in the changed competitive technology and the market scenario, universities are subject to similar pressures like different organizations They have to inculcate and develop a culture so that they have to focus on stakeholders' satisfaction through continuous improvement and educational reforms (Sporn 1999).

Auernhammer and Hall (2013) pointed out that certain factors needed to be in place for knowledge creation, creativity, and innovation to occur. They pointed out that the organization should be open to the idea of change, encourage unusual ideas to be suggested, motivate their staff in intrinsic ways, and challenge and encourage their staff to be innovative. Auernhammer and Hall (2013) also mentioned that the staff should also be willing to experiment to create knowledge and be given the space to do this.

According to Arun and Kumar (2015) one of the characteristics of knowledge management is that it has an impact on people and culture. They also explained that there are some cultural barriers that affect the process of knowledge management. Szczepanska (2014), also mentioned this and explained that organizational culture could promote or hinder the exchange of knowledge.

The culture in public organizations such as universities continues in relationship with traditional models of bureaucracy. Moreover, public sector organizations are fundamentally different from private sector organizations on several dimensions, including diversity of purpose, access to resources, and the nature of organizational constraints.

several studies have shown the importance of organizational culture to support the implementation of the KM process, Because under a knowledge-friendly culture, the implementation of KM practice is more effective and efficient (Adeinat and Abdulfatch 2019, Danish et al. 2012)

Thus, many factors are related to organizational culture, can affect the implementation and success of KM in universities. From the literature, we can deduce the following main elements (Ansari et al. 2012, Cong 2008, Cong & Pandya 2003, Abdullah & Date 2009)

- Trust; - Collaboration, Learning from mistakes, Creativity and innovation, The culture of knowledge sharing.

The various theoretical arguments and empirical studies presented previously allowing us to deduce the first hypothesis :

" There is a positive relationship between the organizational culture and the application of knowledge management at Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of teacher-researchers".

3 ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The term "organizational structure" comes from organizational theory and refers to the hierarchical framework that defines the internal division of labor within an organization (Boussenna, 2021).

Organizational structure refers to the formal arrangement of work roles in an organization and the mechanism of management and integration for work which includes Inter-Organizational activities. It refers to a means to achieve business goals. Corporate goals can be reflected in many aspects concretely. But it can be concluded in two categories including efficiency in stable operation and innovation in dynamic adaptation (Baia et al, 2017).

Gibson et al, (2012) explain that "organizational structure is the pattern of jobs and group of jobs in an organization. An important cause of individual and group behavior ". The organizational structure is the pattern of

work and group work within an organization. Organizational design and structure have always been important factors influencing the behavior of individuals and groups within the organization (Fitria, 2017).

For George and Jones, (2012: 472) "organizational structure is the formal system of task and job reporting relationships. The organizational structure is a formal system, task relations, and job reporting that determines how employees use resources to achieve organizational goals (Fitria, 2017).

Organizational structure is the formal allocation of work roles, administrative mechanism, integrated activities, and setting up of communication channels, authorities, responsibilities, and accountabilities at different levels within the organization (Ajagbe et al , 2016, p. 65; Wahba, 2015, p. 279). In short, it is about how organizational activities are assigned and monitored to achieve organizational objectives. Factors that influence an organization's structure are grouped into two categories: internal and external factors (Tran & Tian, 2013, p. 229). External factors affect structure however, these factors are not in the direct control of the organization whereas the internal factors are measurable, comparable, and directly controlled by the organization (Cetinkaya & rashid , 2018).

So it can be synthesized that the organizational structure is a visualization framework that describes the relationship of organized cooperation regularly with the common goal, which in the framework shows the relationship of authority, responsibility, and cooperation of each part to achieve the goal with indicators: job specification, chain of command, formalization, centralization, and coordination.

3.1 ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE AND KM

There is literature on how organizational structure improves KM efficiency in organizations (Downes, 2014; Mahmoudsalehi, Moradkhannejad, & Sfari, 2012; Yousif, 2012; Allameh, Zare, & Davoodi, 2011; Zheng, Yang, & McLean, 2010).

According to Mahmoudsalehi Moradkhannejad and Safari (2012), organizational structure impacts KM processes as it determines the ways and rates of communication between members of the organization. They further stated that organizational structure specifies a point (place) where the decision is taking in an organization which affects the efficiency and effectiveness of new knowledge implementation. Zheng, Yang, & McLean (2010) said the structural impact on KM improves organizational efficiency, effectiveness, and performance through a pattern of knowledge organization, KM activities coordination, and the degree to which practices of KM are entrenched in routine job processes in an organization. Downes (2014) and Vitari, Moro, Ravarini, and Bourdon (2007) argued that organization structure influences KM efficiency. Furthermore, bureaucratic structure hinders the free flow of information and knowledge. Organizations that are characterized by strong hierarchy structures adversely affect knowledge flow (Umale et al 2020).

In continuation, Riege (2005) and Syed-Ikhsan and Rowland (2004) posit that knowledge transfer flourishes when organizational structure encourages the free flow of information with limited boundaries between business units and management levels. Roper, and Pettit (2002) and Dodgson, (1993) said organizational learning is maximized through the shaping of organizational structure. Yousif (2012) also affirms that the structure of an organization affects KM therefore, organizations should institute a structure that stimulates continuous knowledge sharing and creation. Thus, a decentralized organizational structure is better for organizations as it improves sharing of ideas and interaction which results in the creation of new knowledge. According to Mahmoudsalehi, Moradkhannejad, and Safari (2012), a decentralized organizational structure enhances KM efficiency. On the other hand, a centralized organizational structure negatively affects KM efficiency. In addition, there is a need to adopt a flexible organizational structure that enables the free flow of knowledge in an organization as it enhances knowledge sharing, creation of new knowledge and ultimately improves KM efficiency and organizational performance (Umale et al 2020).

Organizational structure refers to the way in which an organization allocates human resources and tasks in order to achieve its goals (Helms 2006). The organizational structure thus determines the decision-making process as well as the responsibilities for materials, resources, and human processes (Bousenna, 2021).

An organizational structure must be flexible to promote the distribution of ideas and knowledge within the organization. In contrast, a centralized and overly formalized structure will prevent communication between units and the profusion of the distribution of ideas. The communication channels will not favor a fluid diffusion and efficient sharing of knowledge in such a structure. Organizational structure was particularly highlighted as a factor affecting the successful implementation of KM. Thus, horizontal organizations are more convenient for the information and knowledge era due to the flexibility that this type of organization offers (Ansari et al. 2012).

The main factors related to organizational structure identified in the literature are (Ansari et al. 2012, p.215; Cong 2008, p.111; Butler & Murphy 2007, p 615).

- The degree of centralization;
- The degree of formalization;
- Communication flows.

The various theoretical arguments and empirical studies presented previously allowing us to deduce the second hypothesis:

“There is a positive relationship between the organizational structure and the application of knowledge management at Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of teacher-researchers”.

Fig -1: the research model

III. METHODS

1. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Our research is influenced by the inscription of our work in an adequate epistemological paradigm according to the conceptual framework, the hypotheses, the objectives and the relationship between the variables.

In order to be precise, we will respond to all the points mentioned above which summarize our epistemological framework and our methodological choice through the table below:

Table-1 :methodological choices

Methodological axis	Our choice
The Epistemological Paradigm	The post positivism
The current of thought	Scientific realism
the reasoning process	The hypothetical-deductive approach
The working method	It will be quantitative
empirical method of work	The Survey
Data collection tool	The questionnaire

Source :authors

2. DATA COLLECTIO

We administered a questionnaire to a representative sample of 88 teacher-researchers from the various institutions of Abdelmalek Essadi University, the survey was done between September and October 2020.

It seems necessary to us at this point to present an analysis of the sample of our study.

First, we present our sample size calculation:

Table-2 : Sample size calculation

Population size	confidence level	Margin of error	Formula	Our sample size
1000 teacher-researchers	95%	10%	$n = \frac{z^2 \cdot p(1-p)}{1 + (\frac{z^2 \cdot p(1-p)}{2n})}$	n=88 teacher-from different institutions of the university

Source :authors

3. DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT: VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

In order to meet the needs of our study, a questionnaire with nine indices and 40 questions was designed. However, we feel it is necessary to ensure the validity and reliability of our tool.

3.1 CONTENT VALIDITY

In order to ensure the content validity of our questionnaire, we followed the steps below: First, we conducted extensive research on the topic and then specified the structure of the field under study. Then we consulted specialists in the field of knowledge management and management control, primarily.

3.2 ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE RELIABILITY

To address the issue of the reliability of the questions asked in a test, we calculated Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The table below shows the value of the coefficient for all chapters of our research using SPSS software:

Table -3: The reliability of questionnaire

Study Variables	Chapter	Cronbach's α
Creation	1-4	0.822
Storage	5-7	0.838
Sharing	8-11	0.784
Use	12-15	0.971
Knowledge management	1-15	0.957
Organizational culture	36-40	0.906
Organizational Structure	41-45	0.736

From the data in the table above we notice that the value of Cronbach's alpha for all chapters in our research is between 0.784 and 0.977.

For the independent variable the value of alpha = 0.957 while for the dependent variable alpha = 0.973 and 0.906 for Organizational Culture.

Therefore, these values are well above 0.7 which confirms the internal consistency and reliability of our questionnaire.

IV ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

IV.1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

IV.1.1 DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS OF DEPENDENT VARIABLE

For the present research, we were interested in measuring the degree of application of knowledge management (creation - storage - sharing - use). For this we proceeded to the calculation of the averages, the standard deviations of the value of T Student as shown in the following table :

Table -4 : Descriptive results for K.M implementation

K.M operations	The mean	S.D	the T value	level
Knowledge creation	2,23	1,05	19,84	low
Knowledge storage	2,07	1,33	14,65	low
Knowledge sharing	2,71	0,98	25,88	Medium
Knowledge use	2,12	1,14	17,54	low
Overall average	2,29	1,12	19.48	low

The T value in the table = 1.96, with a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, and a mean level between (2.34 and 3.67)

These results clearly illustrate insufficiency application of the K.M operations at the level of the various institutions of the Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of research teachers.

IV.1.2 DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS OF IN DEPENDENT VARIABLE

IV.1.2.1 THE ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

Table-5: Descriptive results for Organizational Culture

the organizational culture	The mean	S.D	Level
The culture of the university encourages teacher-researchers to generate new ideas.	2,09	0,79	Medium
the university provides events that help teachers learn new knowledge.	2,00	0,85	Low
The values and beliefs that circulate at the university Allow errors to be seen as sources of learning.	1,81	0,57	Low
At the university there is a philosophy of promoting collective action for the exchange of ideas and experiences.	1,80	0,83	Low
the culture of the university motivates teacher-researchers to develop their skills and translate them into knowledge.	1,72	0,86	Low
Overall average	1,89	0,67	Low

The T value in the table = 1.96, with a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, and a mean level between (2.34 and 3.67)

According to the above results, we notice that the existing organizational culture at the level of the different institutions of Abdelmalek Essaadi University does not support the application of knowledge management.

IV.1.2. 2THE ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Table -6 : Descriptive results for Organizational structure

The Organizational structure	The mean	S.D	level
At the university, the relationship between the president and subordinates is based on cooperation.	2,45	0,65	Medium
At the university, there is a decentralization of work, which offers the possibility of sharing knowledge between teachers-.	2,09	0,90	Low
The organizational structure of the institution is flexible, which allows for the assimilation of internal and external environmental variables.	2,00	0,60	Low
The organizational structure of the institution allows the circulation of knowledge between departments in a vertical and transversal way.	1,90	0,90	Low
The organizational structure of the institution facilitates the process of personnel turnover, which contributes to the transfer of knowledge.	1,72	0,75	Low
Overall average	2,03	0,54	Low

The T value in the table = 1.96, with a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, and a mean level between (2.34 and 3.67)

According to the above results, we notice that the organizational structure of the different institutions of Abdelmalek Essaadi University does not favor the application of knowledge management.

IV.2 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

4.2.1 TESTING OF THE CENTRAL HYPOTHESIS 1

Table-7 : Correlation coefficient between organizational culture and KM

Axis	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Sig
organizational culture	0.712	0.001

From the table, we notice that the Pearson correlation coefficient value $r = 0.712$ confirms the positive relationship between organizational culture and KM at the different institutions of Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of teacher-researchers with a level of significance α less than 0.05

IV.2.2 TESTING OF THE CENTRAL HYPOTHESIS

Table -8 : Correlation coefficient between organizational structure and KM

axis	Pearson Correlation Coefficient	Sig
organizational structure	0.576	0.000

From the table, we notice that the Pearson correlation coefficient value $r = 0.576$ confirms the positive relationship between organizational structure and KM implementation at the different institutions of Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of teacher-researchers with a level of significance α less than 0.05.

IV.3 DISCUSSIONS

Concerning the success factors of knowledge management, we could show that there is a presence of an unfavorable infrastructure (culture, structure,).

These results coincide with the findings of the work of (Ngulube and Mavodaz, 2012) at metropolitan university new york, the study concluded on the lack of application of knowledge management from the perspective of 79 university officials.

Also, the study of (Al-Mudallal, 2012) concludes on a lack of presence of knowledge management factors at the level of the first Ministry in Jordan from the point of view of the ministry officials.

the work of (Jawad et al, 2010) concludes on the positive impact of organizational factors (leadership - ICT structure - motivational system) in the application of knowledge management at the level of Orange Jordan from the point of view of a sample of 270 civil servants from different departments of Orange Jordan.

Similarly sense the study of (Douza,2008) at the level of the ministry of higher education in Jordan which proves this relationship between the presence of the knowledge management Factors, and its application from the point of view of 300 civil servants.

On the other hand, our results disagree with the results obtained by (Al Talbani et al, 2015) that records a high level of presence of factors (culture, structure, leadership, and ICT) facilitating the application of knowledge management at the level of all universities in the Gaza Strip in Palestine from the point of view of 241 participants between administrators and teachers.

IV.3.1 CONFIRMATORY DISCUSSION OF THE HYPOTHESIZES

IV.3.1 .1 FIRST HYPOTHESIS

The results collected in Table: 7 reflect the presence of an organizational culture not conducive to knowledge management in the various institutions of Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of teachers.

the results coincide with the findings of the study conducted by (Frey et al 2009), which proves the positive role of organizational culture in the success of knowledge management initiatives at the level of German companies from the perspective of a sample of 495 participants.

These results remain inconsistent with the study of (Abdelhadi et al 2015) which proves the existence of an organizational culture conducive to the application of knowledge management at universities in the Gaza Strip in Palestine.

This leads the university leaders to provide more effort to improve the knowledge management culture in Abdelmalek Essaadi University through:

- Promoting values and beliefs that allow mistakes to be considered as Sources of learning.
- The support of a philosophy of promotion of collective action for the exchange of ideas and experiences.
- The motivation of teacher-researchers to develop their skills and translate them into knowledge.

IV.3.1 .1 SECOND HYPOTHESIS

Also the results obtained in the table: 8 clearly indicate that the current organizational structure at the level of different institutions of Abdelmalek Essaadi University from the point of view of teachers is not suitable for the KM implementation at the university.

Note that these results coincide with the findings of the study conducted by (Ghorbani et al,2011) which proves the relationship between knowledge management and organizational structure at the level of the Iranian ministry of education from the point of view of 90 officials.

Therefore, the managers of Abdelmalek Essaadi University institutions are led to improve the current organizational structure to be adequate for the application of knowledge management through:

- Decentralization of work, which offers the possibility of sharing knowledge among teachers-researchers.
- the circulation of knowledge between departments in a vertical and transversal manner.
- staff turnover, which contributes to knowledge transfer.

IV.4 TEST OF THE THEORETICAL MODEL

The figure 2 below presents the results confirming the positive relationship between our variables (Pearson's correlation coefficient is greater than 0.5 for all relationships between variables). This validates both hypotheses of this research and proves the validity of our hypothetical research model :

FIG -2 : TEST OF THE THEORETICAL MODEL

V. CONCLUSION

This article had several objectives, mainly to assess the degree K.M operations application in Moroccan universities through Abdelmalek Essaadi University, and verified the presence of keys factors of success of knowledge management (culture and structure)

according to the theoretical point of view, This article has the particularity of mobilizing a rich theoretical corpus, consisting primarily of the theory of knowledge (Knowledge-Based View), and the approach of keys success factors, linking the success of the application of knowledge management to organizational, technical and human ingredients encompassed in (culture and structure)

In parallel, The empirical phase of our work offers originality in the study of public organizations and precisely universities with a quantitative approach, an approach that is increasingly developed in management science.

In addition, an increase in the size of our samples per establishment could perhaps better explain the influence of K.M for each establishment. In addition, the choice of a single region (Tangier-Tetouan-Al Hoceima) in this article pushes us to expand our field of work for future work to cover the national territory in its entirety.

Additionally in our future work, we will study other success factors of knowledge management initiatives such as management leadership, and information technology.

Moreover, it should be noted that this research has important implications for the leaders of Moroccan universities. The confirmation of the hypotheses of our work reminds us that each university must clearly define its strategy based on better knowledge management as a cornerstone of any action aiming at excellence and organizational performance, and consequently the improvement of its competitiveness at the international level.

also, our research constitutes a line of thought for researchers wishing to strengthen research related to knowledge management in the university environment and especially in Morocco.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Aamoun H., & Sail, S. (2020). *L'impact du capital immatériel sur la performance des entreprises : approche théorique , Revue du contrôle, de la comptabilité et de l'audit « Volume 4 : numéro 2» pp : 109 – 129.*
- [2.] Abidi, W., Sanchez, M., Aoiz, G., (2018), *Phenotypic and biochemical diversity in peach [Prunus persica (L.) Batsch] cultivars. Journal of New Sciences. Agriculture and Biotechnology 51 (5): 3171-3178.*
- [3.] Adeinat, I.M. and Abdulfatah, F.H. (2019), "OC and KM processes: case study in a public university", *VINE Journal of Information and KM Systems*, Vol. 49 No. 1, pp. 35-53, doi: 10.1108/VJKMS-05- 2018-0041.
- [4.] Ahmady, G. A., Nikooravesh, A., & Mehrpour, M. (2016). *Effect of organizational culture on knowledge management based on Denison model. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 230, 387-395.
- [5.] Ajagbe, M. A., Cho, N. M., & Udo, E. E. U. (2016). *How Organizational Structure Aids Business Performance. International Journal Of Research In Commerce & Management*, 7(8), 64-68.
- [6.] Alavi , M ., & Leidner, D. (2001). *Review: Knowledge Management and Knowledge Management Systems: Conceptual Foundations and Research Issues. MIS Quarterly*, 25(1), 107-136. DOI: 10.2307/3250961.
- [7.] Allameh, S.M., Zare, S.M., and Davoodi, S. M. R. (2011). "Examining the Impact of KM Enablers on Knowledge Management Processes." *Procedia Computer Science*, 3, 1211–1223.
- [8.] Al-Mudallal, A. W. (2012), *Impact of Knowledge Management Application on Performance Levels at Palestinian Governmental Institutions: Applied Study Carried at Prime Ministry, unpublished master's dissertation, Islamic University, Gaza.*
- [9.] Al-Talbani, N.; Bdair, R; Al-Ruqub.(2015), *Requirements for Implementing Knowledge Management in the Palestinian Universities in Gaza Strip, Maryland Series in Contemporary Asian Studies. Vol. 2014 Issue 3, p443-480. 38p.*
- [10.] Ansari, M., Youshanlouei, H., Mood, M. (2012). *A Conceptual Model for Success in Implementing Knowledge Management: A Case Study in Tehran Municipality. Journal of Service Science and Management*, 05(02), pp.212–222.
- [11.] Arqawi, M?. Amal, A., Samy S. Abu Naser. Al Shobak, M., (2018) , *Obstacles to the Application of Knowledge Management from the Point of View of the Employees at the Technical University of Palestine, International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research (IJAIRS) ISSN: 2000-002X Vol. 2 Issue 9, September – 2018, Pages: 1-16.*
- [12.] Arun Kumar, D. A. & Kumar, U. (2015). *Knowledge Management: A Review. International Journal of Academic Research In Social Sciences & Humanities*, 4, 2454-2202. [6] Auernhammer, Jan and Hall, Hazel (2014). *Organizational culture in knowledge creation, creativity and innovation: Towards the Freiraum model. Journal of Information Science. 10.1177/0165551513508356.*
- [13.] Auernhammer, Jan and Hall, Hazel (2014). *Organizational culture in knowledge creation, creativity and innovation: Towards the Freiraum model. Journal of Information Science. 10.1177/0165551513508356.*
- [14.] Baia, W., Fengb, Y., Yuea, Y., & Fenga, (2017), *Organizational Structure, Cross-Functional Integration and Performance of New Product Development Team, 13th Global Congress on Manufacturing and Management, GCMM 2016.*
- [15.] Barakat, Ziad and Hassan, Kifah (2009). "Future Development Needs of Graduate Students in Education in Palestinian Universities". *Research presented to the first conference of the Deanship of Scientific Research at An-Najah National University, Nablus.*
- [16.] BOUSSENA, Y. (2021). *Knowledge management and academic performance moderating role of organizational structure: Abdelmalek essaadi university case. International Journal of Financial Accountability, Economics, Management, and Auditing (IJFAEMA)*, 3(3), 145-158. <https://doi.org/10.52502/ijfaema.v3i3.61>.
- [17.] Bratianu, C.; Hadad, S.; Bejinaru, R. (2020), *Paradigm shift in business education: A competence-based approach. Sustainability* , 12, 1348. [CrossRef].
- [18.] Bratianu, C.; Pinzaru, F. (2015), *University governance as a strategic driving force. In Proceedings of the 11th European Conference on Management, Leadership, and Governance, Military Academy, Lisbon, Portugal; Dias, J.C., Ed.; Academic Conferences and Publishing International: Reading, UK, pp. 28–35.*
- [19.] Bratianu, C.; Stanescu, D.F.; Mocanu, R. (2021) , *Exploring the Knowledge Management Impact on Business Education. Sustainability*, 13, 2313. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042313>.
- [20.] Butler, T., Murphy, C. (2007). *Implementing Knowledge Management Systems in Public Sector Organisations: A Case Study of Critical Success Factors. In H. Österle, J. Schelp, & R. Winter, eds. 15th European Conference on Information Systems. University of St. Gallen, pp. 612–623.*
- [21.] Cetinkaya , A., rashid, M, (2018) , *The Effect of Social Media on Employees' Job Performance: The mediating Role of Organizational Structure, Online at https://mpr.aub.uni-muenchen.de/91354/ MPRA Paper No. 91354, posted 09 Jan 2019.*
- [22.] Chandradewini. (2017), "The analysis of Organizational Culture of the Revenue Department of Cimahi City, West Java, Indonesia", *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 6 (3), 301-304.
- [23.] Cong, X., (2008). *Towards a framework of knowledge management in the chinese public sector: a case study of china customs. Northumbria University.*

- [24.]Costa , V., Monteiro. (2016). *Key knowledge management processes for innovation: a systematic literature review*, VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems , ISSN: 2059-5891.
- [25.]Danish, R.Q., Munir, Y. and Butt, S.S.D. (2012), "Moderating role of OC between KM and organizational effectiveness in service sector", *World Applied Sciences Journal*, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 45-53.
- [26.]Dimensions and Knowledge Management (KM) in Educational Organization, *Journal of World Applied*
- [27.]Doueihy, M. (2009). *La grande conversion numérique* Seuil, Paris, 271 , <https://doi.org/10.4074/S0336150009002129>
- [28.]Douza, S, (2008), *The relationship between Knowledge management requirements and its impact on institutional performance excellence*, Master Unpublished MA, Middle East Studies University Olaya, Amman.
- [29.]Downes, T. V., & Downes, T. (2014). *An Evaluation of Knowledge Management Practices in Nonprofit Community Services Organisations in Australia*. Southern Cross University.
- [30.] Eskiler, E., Ekici, S., Soyer, F. and Sari, I. (2016), "The relationship between OC and innovative work behavior for sports services in tourism enterprisesPhysical culture and sport", *Studies and Research*, Vol. 69 No. 1, pp. 53-64.
- [31.]Fitria, H., Mukhtar, M., & Akbar, M. (2017). THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE AND LEADERSHIP STYLE ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL. *IJHCM (International Journal of Human Capital Management)*, 1(02), 101-112. <https://doi.org/10.21009/IJHCM.01.02.12>.
- [32.]Frey, P., Lindner, F., Müller, F. and Wald, A. 2009. *Project Knowledge Management Organizational Design and Success Factors- an Empirical Study in Germany*, *Proceedings of the 42nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp.1-15.
- [33.]Garcia-Perez, A.; Cegarra-Navarro, J.G.; Bedford, D.; Thomas, M.; Wakabayashi, S. *Critical Capabilities and Competencies for Knowledge Organizations*; Emerald Publishing: Bingley, UK, 2020.
- [34.]George, J and Gareth R., (2012). *Understanding and Managing Organizational Behavior*. New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- [35.]Ghorbani,M., Noghabi, J. and Nikoukar,M.(2011) . *Relationship Between Organizational Structure*
- [36.]Gibson,J., Ivancevich, J, Donelly, Ja., and Robert, K., (2012). *Organizations: Behaviour, Structure, Processes*. New York: McGraw-Hill-Irwin.
- [37.]Goran,I & Sağsanb, M.,(2021) *The Mediation Effect of Organizational Culture between Knowledge Management Processes and Creative Thinking: A Case of COVID 19 Healthcare Workers in Northern Iraq* Goran Yousif Ismaela , Mustafa Sağsanb, *Revista Argentina de Clínica Psicológica* 2021, Vol. XXX, N°1, 658-667 DOI: 10.24205/03276716.2020.2061.
- [38.]Handa, P.; Pagani, J.; Bedford, D. *Knowledge Assets and Knowledge Audits*; Emerald Publishing: Bingley, UK, 2019.
- [39.]Jawad,N., Mousa, Sabah,M., Al Modan, S., (2009). *Measuring the Impact of Organizational Culture on the Implementation of Knowledge Management in the Jordanian Communication Group (Orange): Case Study*, *Humanities Journal*, Issue,44, 106:142.
- [40.]Khan, M.A., Ismail, F.B., Hussain, A. and Alghazali, B. (2020), "The interplay of leadership styles, innovative work behavior, OC, and organizational citizenship behavior", *Sage Open*, Vol. 10 No. 1, 2158244019898264.
- [41.]Lichtarski,J., (2009) ,*Organizational Structure and Knowledge Management*. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286590837_Organizational_Structure_and_Knowledge_Management . *Argumenta Oeconomica*.
- [42.]Mahmoudsalehi, M., Moradkhannejad, R., & Safari, K. (2012). *How Knowledge Management is Affected by Organizational Structure*. *Learning Organization*, 19(6), 518-528.
- [43.]Maurice Thévenet, (2006) , *La culture d'entreprise*, 5e édition.
- [44.]Nanjundeswaraswamy,T & swamy,D., (2021), *Knowledge management processes and organizational culture in the higher educational technical institutions*, *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences* , DOI 10.1108/JEAS-07-2020-0134.
- [45.]Nonaka, I., (1994). *A Dynamic Theory of Organizational Knowledge Creation*. *Organization Science*, 5(1), pp.14-37.
- [46.]Quinn, R.E. (1988), *Beyond Rational Management: Mastering the Paradoxes and Competing Demands of High Performance*, Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, CA, 978-1555423773.
- [47.]Ranjan , J., & Bhatnagar, V., (2008). *Principles for successful aCRM in organizations*, *Direct Marketing An International Journal* 2(4):239-247, DOI: 10.1108/17505930810931035.
- [48.]Riege, A. (2005). "Three-dozen knowledge-sharing barriers managers must consider." *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 9(3), 18-35.
- [49.]Roper, L & Pettit, J. (2002). "Development and the learning Organisation: an Introduction." *Development in Practice*, 12(3/4), 258-271.
- [50.]Schein , E , (2004) , *organizational culture and leadership* , Series. HD58.7.
- [51.]*Sciences*, 12(11):2032-2040.
- [52.]Shattock, M. 2006 *Managing Good Governance in Higher Education*; Open University Press: Berkshire, UK. 42. Maxwell, N. *From knowledge to wisdom: The need for an academic revolution*. In *Wisdom in the University*; Barnett, R., Maxwell, N., Eds.; Routledge: New York, NY, USA, 2008; pp. 1-20. 43.

- [53.] Syed-Ikhsan, SOS & Rowland, F. (2004). "Knowledge management in a public organization: a study on the relationship between organizational elements and the performance of knowledge transfer." *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 8(2), 95–111.
- [54.] Szczepańska-Woszczyzna, K. (2014). The importance of organizational culture for innovation in the company. *Forum Scientiae Oeconomia*, 2, 27-39.
- [55.] Tran, Q., & Tian, Y. (2013). Organizational Structure: Influencing Factors and Impact on a Firm. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 3, 229-236.
- [56.] Umale, O., Mansor, M., Marhiza, I. (2020), ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE IN KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY AND TAX ADMINISTRATION PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF FEDERAL INLAND REVENUE SERVICE NIGERIA, *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, United Kingdom, Vol. VIII, Issue 3.
- [57.] Wahba, M. (2015). The Impact Of Organizational Structure On Knowledge Management Processes In Egyptian Context. *Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(3), 275-292.
- [58.] Widjaja, J., & Kuslinan B, (2018), The Role of Organizational Culture and Knowledge Management to Encourage Innovation in Governance in an Indonesian Private University, *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, Vol. 7, Supplementary Issue 1, ISSN: 2304-1013 .
- [59.] Yousif, L. A. (2012). Knowledge Management Implementation, Innovation, and Organisational Performance: An Empirical Study in the Iraqi Mobile Telecommunication Sector. *Universiti Utara Malaysia*.
- [60.] Zheng, W., Yang, B., McLean, N. G. (2010). Linking Organizational Culture, Structure, Strategy, and Organizational Effectiveness: Mediating Role of Knowledge Management. *Journal of Business Research*, 63(7), 763–77